

Novel Hybrid approach for Lung cancer detection

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ABSTRACT: One of the most prevalent illnesses that may be treated early to increase a patient's chances of survival is lung disease. The most difficult step for the radiologist is making the cancer diagnosis. For radiologists, an effective computer-aided system is especially beneficial. Even though lung cancer is the deadliest type of the illness, early detection is crucial for a good prognosis and successful treatment. This paper is an empirical review of studies examining symptoms in individuals with lung cancer. Medical image analysis is necessary for the early detection of various disorders, which would help physicians treat patients effectively. In this paper we are focusing on the selection of the weights in enhanced Elman spike neural network (EESNN) in optimal way. To enhance the optimal solution Hunter, pray optimization (HPO) is used. Experimental results shows that overall accuracy (98.81%) in lung cancer detection increased due to hunter pray optimization algorithm.

Keywords: Lung cancer, medical image analysis, Enhanced Elman spike neural network

1. INTRODUCTION:

Lung cancer is one of the most common cancers we have and a large number of people die of this disease every year. The disease is often discovered in a late stage, but also in earlier stages lung cancer patients have worse outcome than patients with other cancers. Even without spreading to other organs, during stage I, the survival rate of lung cancer is under 70%. In comparison, for example, breast cancer there is 95% survival in stage [1]

According to the Global Cancer Observatory database developed by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) in 2018, lung cancer was the leading cause of death for men and the third leading cause of death for women. Incidence and death rates for 36 cancer types and 185 countries were included in the database. 2018 saw about 1.8 million cancer-related deaths, or around 18.4% of all cancer-related deaths [2]. A number of cancer control research and early detection methods have been created to lower mortality because of the startling rise in lung cancer deaths and the disease's abnormally high occurrence in nature.

For the majority of individuals with lung cancer, lymph nodes are the initial site of dissemination. Assessing lymph node spread before surgery is crucial for thinking about further treatment options. During surgery, lymph nodes will be removed so they may be examined under a light microscope. The patient is given more treatment if there are tumor cell patches in the lymph nodes. Patients have a poor survival rate even after being diagnosed, and most of the time the spread of cancer to lymph nodes goes undetected since clinical procedures are insensitive. This requires more sophisticated and sensitive techniques. Like all other malignancies, lung cancer arises from an acquired anomaly in the body's fundamental life unit.

When DNA alterations occur in lung cells, lung cancer results. The instructions that inform a cell what to do are encoded in its DNA. The DNA of healthy cells provides instructions for growth and multiplication at a certain rate. The cells are instructed to die at a specific moment. Different instructions are sent by the DNA alterations in cancer cells. The alterations instruct the cancer cells to proliferate rapidly. When healthy cells would perish, cancer cells can survive. Too many cells are produced as a result. A tumour may develop from the cancer cells. Healthy bodily tissue may be invaded and destroyed by the tumour as it grows. Cancer cells have the ability to separate throughout time and travel to other areas of the body.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY:

One of the most important factors in maintaining their health and quality of life is healthcare. A essential right that promotes health and protects against many diseases is access to high-quality healthcare. In addition to meeting the requirements of disadvantaged populations, healthcare systems are crucial for tackling a variety of public health concerns. Numerous technological and medical advancements are improving healthcare systems, expanding access to treatment, and reducing costs. For men, the lifetime risk of lung cancer is 1 in 13; for women, it is 1 in 16.

Therefore, detection prediction may help patients and healthcare professionals with treatment intensity, cost control, Significant progress has been made in the identification of lung cancer [3], but further study is required to create methods that are broadly and practically applicable to medical applications. This could eventually result in better decisions regarding the efforts of family members and medical professionals to enhance the health of a cancer patient.

For these reasons, scientists, physicians, and computer engineers are interested in the proble

of lung cancer diagnosis.

In order to be applied in a wide range of domains, including healthcare for cancer detection, disease diagnosis, object detection, feature extraction, and image classification, among others, machine learning and deep learning algorithms apply different transformations to both small and large databases. Numerous classification and regression problems are resolved by Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Random Forests (RF), and Nearest Neighbors (NN) [4]. These techniques have been used on several datasets because of their exceptional job management, performance, and prediction capabilities.

Diverse systems have already established a number of lung cancer detection techniques. In their presentation of SVM-based classification for the detection of lung cancer, Nascimento et al. achieved a 92.78% accuracy rate. Sheway et al. [5] used histogram and geometric characteristics to categorize nodules. Farag et al. [6] investigated the standardization of lung cancer categorization using the concept of feature fusion. For feature extraction, k-nearest neighbors (kNN) and support vector machines (SVMs) were used after Local Binary Pattern (LBP), Gabor filter, and Signed-distance transform shape-based feature descriptors.

Image processing methods have previously been used to study lung cancer detection. Deep learning methods and neural networks have recently been used to the field of medical imaging. Numerous studies [7-9] have attempted to use machine learning and neural networks for lung cancer detection and classification. There aren't many deep learning methods used to identify lung cancer. This is a result of the dearth of extensive medical picture datasets, particularly for lung cancer. Urine samples are used by Shimizu et al. [10] to identify lung cancer.

According to statistics, lung cancer is the second most prevalent cancer diagnosed in both men and women and the most common kind of cancer that results in mortality [11], [12]. The two primary subtypes of lung cancer are non-small cell carcinoma (NSCLC), the most frequently diagnosed form of the disease, which develops slowly, and small cell carcinoma (SCLC), which grows quickly but is uncommon. Weight loss, chest discomfort, dyspnea, and chronic cough are all signs of lung cancer. [13,14,15] Physical examination, several imaging modalities, and molecular testing to identify precise genetic alterations or biomarkers to aid in choosing the most effective treatment choices are among the diagnostic approaches for lung cancer. Recent developments in genome profiling techniques have greatly enhanced our

understanding of how cancer develops at the molecular level and aided in the discovery of biomarkers for lung cancer and other cancers [16].

The radiologist's ability to provide a prompt and precise diagnosis is closely correlated with the quality and accuracy of the pictures. To forecast lung cancer, deep learning techniques are also used [17]. Features are automatically derived from training photos. Deep learning is less expensive than traditional CAD frameworks in comparison. The radiologist benefits from deep learning's ability to provide HD representation of the input data, which speeds up the detection and identification process. Since malignant and non-cancerous regions are identified based on pixel data, each pixel in the picture immediately aids in the diagnosis of cancer. Therefore, deep learning helps doctors better serve the healthcare system by helping them identify and classify diseases.

The Convolutional Layers can extract unique information from the provided photos of cancer cells by using various convolution filters [18]. Image processing is the initial stage of the process under the approach being explained, when preprocessing techniques are applied to enhance the quality of medical pictures. The enhanced images are then subjected to segmentation, a crucial step in locating relevant regions in lung imaging. After being identified, the areas are put through a procedure called feature extraction, which entails removing important elements in order to find important patterns that may indicate lung cancer.

3. SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT:

Preventing the development and spread of cancer cells requires early cancer diagnosis. The odds of survival are significantly greater, and more treatment options are available when cancer is discovered early. Cancer is analysed using a variety of imaging techniques, including computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and chest X-rays. A slice-like picture, in which some nodules are spherical but not necessarily malignant, was created by the computer by combining many precise CT scan images. Tumour examination by the radiologist is therefore a challenging and time-consuming process.

The Flamingo Search Optimization Algorithm:

The social behavior and foraging habits of flamingos, particularly in their quest for food in challenging surroundings, served as the inspiration for the Flamingo Search Algorithm (FSA), an optimization approach. Feature selection in machine learning and data mining is one of the real-world uses for FSA, which has become a promising method in optimization. Finding the most informative subset of features that improve predictive model performance while lowering dimensionality, computational expenses, and overfitting is the goal of feature

selection. The concepts of flamingo behavior that FSA uses to assist flamingos obtain food in wetlands effectively include flocking, prey tracking, and food seeking. Usually, the algorithm comprises stages that mimic.

Figure 1: Block Diagram as per method

The migratory and foraging habits of flamingos served as the inspiration for the Flamingo search method (FSA), a swarm intelligence optimization method. It is a relatively recent meta-heuristic algorithm that balances local exploitation with global exploration to tackle complicated optimization issues. [19,20]

Usually, the algorithm comprises stages that mimic:

Flamingos' foraging behavior: Involves analyzing their surroundings to determine whether locations have a higher density of food.

Tracking Prey: To increase their food intake, flamingos hone their hunt by paying attention to the locations of other birds.

Communication and Decision-Making: Flamingos balance exploration and exploitation by moving in reaction to their environment and other people's behaviors.

4. RESULT ANALYSIS:

The proposed work is using hybrid approach consisting of Flamingo Search Optimization Algorithm and Enhanced elman spike neural network (EESNN). Analyse an image's pattern and evaluate whether it is recognized using the Improved Elman Spike Neural Network. Additionally, when looking at an image, seek for other patterns. A neural network for the network to recognize, understand, and classify the picture, training requires a predefined data set. Images are categorized and patterns are found using the Enhanced Elman Spike Neural Network (EESNN) [21]. The EESNN classifier does not reflect any adaptation of optimization procedures to establish the ideal parameters to provide an accurate Lung Cancer Classification system.

Various features are extracted during feature extraction with the help of GLCM window adaptive approach from the segmented images. Then the extracted features are provided to the EESNN optimized with flamingo search optimization. Here, EESNN is deemed to classify the lung tumour. Work is evaluated using the standard database. IQ-OTH/NCCD Lung Cancer Dataset. The dataset consists of 1190 CT images, categorized into Normal consisting of 55 cases, Benign cases are 15 and Malignant 40 cases were considered. The images are in DICOM format and contain 80–200 slices per case.

Figure 2. Representation of lung cancer images

Figure 1 represents the types lung cancer images in dataset including Image a as normal, Image b as benign and Image c as a malignant image.

Table 1.1 Performance evaluation of proposed work.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	F1-Score (%)
SVM	74	73	74	74
GoogleNet-DNN	77	79	78	76
CNN	82	87	83	81
Proposed EESNN-FSOA	99.12	98.23	98.12	98.5

Graph 1: Comparative analysis of proposed work.

In Table 1.1 results are shown, where performance evaluation is represented using accuracy, precision, specificity and F1-Score . The EESNN-FSOA method achieved 99.12% accuracy.

5. CONCLUSION:

In order to properly treat lung cancer, which is a dangerous and occasionally deadly illness, early detection is essential. When compared to the most advanced techniques, the suggested CADE system exhibits encouraging outcomes in the early diagnosis of lung cancer. Additional datasets will be examined in the future to test the suggested system's resilience. By automating the detection and classification of lung cancer, deep learning algorithms lessen the strain of medical practitioners. The combination of EESNN and FSOA creates a highly efficient and reliable model for medical image analysis.in future can aapply deep reinforcement learning for adaptive model training

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